

**A SHORT SIMPLE PROBABILISTIC PROOF OF A WELL KNOWN
IDENTITY AND THE DERIVATION OF RELATED NEW
IDENTITIES INVOLVING THE BERNOULLI NUMBERS AND
THE EULER NUMBERS**

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Abstract

An alternative short, elementary probabilistic and combinatorial proof is presented to derive a closed form expression for $I_k := (1/\pi) \int_0^\infty (\sin^k x)/x^k dx$, a well known identity in the literature. An alternative simpler and more elegant form for the value of I_k is also obtained for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$, generalizing a result derived by R. Butler in 1960. Furthermore, our results show new relations between I_k , the Dirichlet beta functions, the Bernoulli numbers, and the Euler numbers in a way not realized before.

1. Introduction

The integral I_k appears in a number of diverse problems (see, e.g., [2, 4, 7, 8, 9, 11, 17, 19, 21]).

In closed form, I_k is given (see, e.g., [8]) for all integers $k \geq 1$ by

$$I_k = \frac{1}{2^k (k-1)!} \sum_{i=0}^{\gamma_{k/2}} (-1)^i \binom{k}{i} (k-2i)^{k-1}, \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma_s := \lfloor s \rfloor = \text{Floor}(s)$. The values of the first ten values of I_k are:

$$\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{8}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{115}{384}, \frac{11}{40}, \frac{5887}{23040}, \frac{151}{630}, \frac{259723}{1146880}, \frac{15619}{72576}.$$

The numerators and denominators of these ratios are the sequences OEIS A049330 and OEIS A049331, respectively.

Several rather tedious mathematical methods have been suggested in the literature to prove the identity in Equation (1). For example, Goddard’s approach in his version in [7] is based on a relation which is given by

$$\log\left(\frac{\sin x}{x}\right) = -\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{B_i}{2i(2i)!} (2x)^{2i},$$

where the B_i ’s are the Bernoulli numbers. The values of these numbers are $B_0 = 1, B_2 = 1/6, B_4 = -1/30, B_6 = 1/42, B_8 = -1/30, B_{10} = 5/66$, etc. (see OEIS A000367 and OEIS A002445). All odd-indexed Bernoulli numbers are zero, except for the convention that $B_1 = -1/2$ is used, and the signs of B_{2n} alternate. Butler applies in [2] a formula due to Poisson (see, e.g., [20, p.443]) to derive Equation (1) by the trapezoidal rule using certain ranges of intervals, dependent on k . He also presented the following alternative and simpler form for the value of I_k in the cases $1 \leq k \leq 4$:

$$I_k = \frac{1}{4} \left\{ \frac{E_{k-1}}{(k-1)!} + 1 \right\}, \tag{2}$$

where E_{k-1} represents the appropriate Eulerian numbers, which are those used in [10], namely, $E_0 = 1, E_1 = 1, E_2 = 1, E_3 = 2, E_4 = 5, E_5 = 16, E_6 = 61, E_7 = 272, E_8 = 1385, E_9 = 7936, E_{10} = 50521$, etc.

Below we provide an alternative elementary probabilistic and combinatorial proof of the identity in Equation (1). Also, a simpler form for I_k is derived for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$. Furthermore, some interesting relations between I_k , the Dirichlet beta functions, the Bernoulli numbers, and the Euler numbers are discussed.

2. Alternative Proof

We first introduce some notation. Suppose that U_1, U_2, \dots, U_k are independent and identically distributed uniform random variables on $(0, 1)$. Let $V_i = 2U_i - 1, i = 1, \dots, k$. Then clearly V_1, V_2, \dots, V_k are independent and identically distributed uniform variables on $(-1, +1)$, with probability density function

$$g(y) = \begin{cases} 1/2, & \text{for } -1 < y < +1; \\ 0, & \text{elsewhere.} \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Define $S_k := \sum_{i=1}^k U_i, T_k := \sum_{i=1}^k V_i = 2S_k - k$, and denote the cumulative distribution function of S_k and that of T_k by F_k and G_k , respectively, with corresponding probability density functions f_k and g_k , which exist almost everywhere since F_k and G_k are absolutely continuous with respect to Lebesgue measure.

Theorem 1. *The identity in Equation (1) holds for all integers $k \geq 1$.*

Proof. Note that

$$\begin{aligned} G_k(t) &= P(T_k \leq t) = P(2S_k - k \leq t) \\ &= P(S_k \leq (t+k)/2) = F_k((t+k)/2), \end{aligned}$$

so that, since $0 < S_k < k$ and $-k < T_k < k$,

$$g_k(t) := \frac{d}{dt}G_k(t) = \begin{cases} (1/2)f_k((t+k)/2), & \text{for } -k < t < k; \\ 0, & \text{elsewhere.} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

The distribution of S_k , the sum of independent and identically distributed uniform random variables on $(0, 1)$, is well known in the statistical literature (see, e.g., [1,12,13,14,15,16]). From Remark 3 in [16, p.175] it follows for example that

$$f_k(s) := \frac{d}{ds}F_k(s) = \frac{1}{(k-1)!} \sum_{i=0}^{\gamma_s} (-1)^i \binom{k}{i} (s-i)^{k-1}, \tag{5}$$

for $0 < s < k$. Hence, applying Equations (4) and (5) we therefore have that

$$g_k(t) = \frac{1}{2^k(k-1)!} \sum_{i=0}^{\gamma_k(t)} (-1)^i \binom{k}{i} (t+k-2i)^{k-1}, \tag{6}$$

where $\gamma_k(t) := \lfloor (t+k)/2 \rfloor$. The following interesting identity can now be deduced from Equations (5) and (6):

$$g_k(0) = I_k. \tag{7}$$

Furthermore, since the V_j 's, $j = 1, \dots, k$, are identically distributed, they have a common characteristic function, that is (see Equation (3)),

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_j(t) &:= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{itv} g(v) dv, \quad (i^2 = -1) \\ &= \frac{\sin t}{t} \quad (t \in \mathcal{R}). \end{aligned}$$

Using the fact that the V_j 's are independent random variables, it follows that the characteristic function $C_k(t)$ of $T_k := \sum_{i=1}^k V_i$ is given by

$$C_k(t) := \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{itv} g_k(v) dv = \prod_{j=1}^k \varphi_j(t) = \left(\frac{\sin t}{t} \right)^k. \tag{8}$$

Applying the Fourier integral inversion theorem (see Equation (15.20) in [20, p.937]), from Equation (8) we obtain

$$g_k(v) := \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-itv} C_k(t) dt = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-itv} \left(\frac{\sin t}{t} \right)^k dt,$$

which implies that

$$g_k(0) := \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{\sin t}{t}\right)^k dt = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} \left(\frac{\sin t}{t}\right)^k dt. \tag{9}$$

Hence, Equation (1) follows from Equations (7) and (9). □

3. Simplified and New Identities for $I_k, k = 2, 4, 6, 8$

We need the following known results, which are stated as propositions.

Proposition 1 ([5]). *Let $\zeta(s) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n^s, s > 1$, be the Riemann zeta function, then*

$$\zeta(k) = \frac{(2\pi)^k}{2(k!)} |B_k|, \quad (k = 2, 4, 6, \dots). \tag{10}$$

Proposition 2 ([20]). *We have*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^k} = (1 - 2^{-k})\zeta(k), \quad k > 1. \tag{11}$$

To state the next proposition, we need the following definitions. Let $\beta(k) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-1}/(2n-1)^k$ be the well-known Dirichlet beta function, and suppose $\{E_k, k = 0, 2, 4, \dots\}$ is the set of Euler numbers (OEIS A028296) for the rest of the discussion below.

Proposition 3 ([3,6]). *For each even $k \geq 2$, we have*

$$\beta(k-1) = \left(\frac{\pi^{k-1}}{2^k}\right) \frac{|E_{k-2}|}{(k-2)!}, \tag{12}$$

which can be rewritten as $\beta(k-1) = r\pi^{k-1}$ for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8, \dots$, where the multiples r are respectively (OEIS A046976 and OEIS A053005):

$$1/4, 1/32, 5/1536, 61/184320, \dots$$

Proposition 4 ([18]). *We have*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin^k(nt)}{n^k} = \pi t^{k-1} I_k - \frac{t^k}{2}, \tag{13}$$

for $0 < t < 2\pi$ if $k = 1$, and $0 \leq t \leq 2\pi/k$ if $k \geq 2$.

Note that in [18] the notation \tilde{S}_k is used instead of I_k .

3.1. Relation Between I_k and the Bernoulli Numbers for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$

Let $t = \pi/4$. Straightforward calculations then show that, since k is even, Equation (13) becomes

$$\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^k \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^k} + \frac{1}{2^k} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^k} = \frac{\pi^k}{2^{2k-2}} \left(I_k - \frac{1}{8}\right). \tag{14}$$

Hence, from Equations (10), (11) and (14) we obtain the following interesting new identity for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$:

$$I_k = \frac{1}{8} \left\{ \frac{2^k(2^k - 1)(2^{k/2} + 1)}{k!} |B_k| + 1 \right\}. \tag{15}$$

3.2. Relation Between I_k and the Euler Numbers for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$

Differentiating with respect to t the left-hand side of Equation (13) term by term (which is permissible by virtue of the uniform convergence of the resulting sum and continuity of $\sin x$ and $\cos x$) and the right-hand side of Equation (13), we obtain

$$k \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin^{k-1}(nt) \cos(nt)}{n^{k-1}} = (k-1)\pi t^{k-2} I_k - \frac{kt^{k-1}}{2}. \tag{16}$$

Choosing $t = \pi/4$ in Equation (16), it readily follows, since $k - 1$ is odd, that

$$k \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^{k-1} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \beta(k-1) = \frac{\pi^{k-1}}{2^{2k-1}} [8(k-1)I_k - k],$$

which yields the following surprising identity for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$:

$$\beta(k-1) = 2^{(2-3k)/2} \pi^{k-1} [8(k-1)I_k - k] / k. \tag{17}$$

Furthermore, from Equations (12) and (17) the following exciting identity is also obtained for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$:

$$I_k = \frac{k}{8(k-1)} \left\{ \frac{2^{(k-2)/2} |E_{k-2}|}{(k-2)!} + 1 \right\}. \tag{18}$$

Note that both the expressions for I_k presented in Equations (2) and (18) yield that $I_2 = 1/2$ and $I_4 = 1/3$. However, the formula for I_k given in Equation (18) is a generalization to the cases $k = 6$ and $k = 8$ of the identity for I_k in Equation (2), derived in [2].

3.3. Relation Between B_k and E_k for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$

From Equations (15) and (18) it readily follows that for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$,

$$2^k(2^k - 1)(2^{k/2} + 1)|B_k| = k^2 2^{(k-2)/2} |E_{k-2}| + k(k - 2)!,$$

which also seems to be a new identity in the literature.

3.4. I_k Expressed as a Function of Both B_k and E_k for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$

Rewrite Equation (13) in terms of x , i.e.,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin^k(nx)}{n^k} = \pi x^{k-1} I_k - \frac{x^k}{2}, \tag{19}$$

for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$. Since k is even, a well known trigonometric identity is given by

$$\sin^k(nx) = \frac{1}{2^k} \binom{k}{k/2} + \frac{2}{2^k} \sum_{i=0}^{(k-2)/2} (-1)^{(k-2i)/2} \binom{k}{i} \cos((k - 2i)nx), \tag{20}$$

which can be deduced using De Moivre’s identity, Euler’s formula and the binomial theorem.

Substituting the expression for $\sin^k(nx)$ in Equation (20) into the left-hand side of Equation (19), and then integrating both sides of the resulting identity (term by term) with respect to x over the intervals $(0, t)$ (which is permissible by virtue of the uniform convergence of the sum and continuity of $\sin x$ and $\cos x$), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2^k} \binom{k}{k/2} t \zeta(k) + \frac{2}{2^k} \sum_{i=0}^{(k-2)/2} \frac{(-1)^{(k-2i)/2}}{(k - 2i)} \binom{k}{i} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin((k - 2i)nt)}{n^{k+1}} \\ = \frac{\pi t^k I_k}{k} - \frac{t^{k+1}}{2(k + 1)}. \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Choosing $t = \pi/4$ in Equation (21), we then have that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2^k} \binom{k}{k/2} (\pi/4) \zeta(k) + \frac{1}{2^k} \sum_{j=1}^{k/2} \frac{(-1)^j}{j} \binom{k}{(k - 2j)/2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(jn\pi/2)}{n^{k+1}} \\ = \frac{\pi^{k+1}}{4^k} \left\{ \frac{I_k}{k} - \frac{1}{8(k + 1)} \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Applying Equation (10), the first term on the left-hand side of Equation (22) equals

$$\frac{\binom{k}{k/2} \pi^{k+1} |B_k|}{8(k!)}, \tag{23}$$

and it readily follows, since $k \leq 8$, that the second term on the left-hand side of Equation (22) becomes

$$\beta(k+1) \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \binom{k}{(k-6)/2} - \binom{k}{(k-2)/2} \right\} / 2^k, \tag{24}$$

with $\binom{k}{j} = 0$ for $j < 0$ and $\binom{k}{0} = 1$.

Note that replacing k by $k + 2$ in Equation (12) we have that

$$\beta(k+1) = \left(\frac{\pi^{k+1}}{2^{k+2}}\right) \frac{|E_k|}{k!}. \tag{25}$$

Hence, from Equations (22), (23), (24), and (25) we obtain the following unexpected new identity for $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$:

$$I_k = \frac{4^k \binom{k}{k/2} |B_k|}{8(k-1)!} + \frac{|E_k|}{4(k-1)!} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \binom{k}{(k-6)/2} - \binom{k}{(k-2)/2} \right\} + \frac{k}{8(k+1)}.$$

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